

ISic1509

I.Sicily inscription 1509

Language

Punic

Type

building

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Eryx

Place of origin (modern)

Erice

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Erice

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645010

Bibliography

Académie des inscriptions et belles-lettres, 1881-1962. *Corpus inscriptionum Semiticarum*. Paris. At 1.136

Amadasi Guzzo, M.G. 1967. *Le iscrizioni fenicie e puniche delle colonie in Occidente*. Rome. At Sic.Pun.06

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. Notizie degli scavi di antichità. At 254-259 tav. 1-2

Salinas, A. 1884. *Studi storici e archeologici sulla Sicilia*. Palermo. At 119-130

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